

Hydrogen sampling systems adapted to heavy-duty refuelling stations' current and future specifications – A review

Karine Arrhenius^{a,*}, Thomas Bacquart^b, Thor Aarhaug^c, Stefan Persijn^d, Oliver Bükler^a, Danique van Workum^d, Annarita Baldan^d, Sven Kaiser^e, Maxime Dufond^f, Quentin Nouvelot^f, Rémy Maury^g

^a Research Institutes of Sweden AB (RISE), Frans Perssons väg, Göteborg 412 76, Sweden

^b National Physical Laboratory (NPL), Hampton Road, Teddington, Middlesex TW11 0LW, United Kingdom

^c SINTEF Industry, Richard Birkelandsvei 2b, Trondheim 7034, Norway

^d VSL, National Metrology institute, Thijsseweg 11, JA Delft 2629, the Netherlands

^e ZBT, Zentrum für BrennstoffzellenTechnik, Carl-Benz-Str. 201, Duisburg 47057, Germany

^f ENGIE, Research Center ENGIE LAB CRIGEN, 4 rue Joséphine Baker, 93240 Stains and 15 quai Louis Aulagne, St-Fons 69190, France

^g CESAME EXADEBIT, 43 rue de l'aérodrome, Poitiers 86000, France

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Hydrogen
Hydrogen purity
Heavy-duty applications
Sampling systems
Standardization

ABSTRACT

To meet the new regulation for the deployment of alternative fuels infrastructure which sets targets for electric recharging and hydrogen refuelling infrastructure by 2025 or 2030, a large infrastructure comprising truck-suitable hydrogen refuelling stations will soon be required. However, further standardisation is required to support the uptake of hydrogen for heavy-duty transport for Europe's green energy future. Hydrogen-powered vehicles require pure hydrogen as some contaminants can reduce the performance of the fuel cell even at very low levels. Even if previous projects have paved the way for the development of the European quality infrastructure for hydrogen conformity assessment, sampling systems and methods have yet to be developed for heavy-duty hydrogen refuelling stations (HD-HRS). This study reviews different aspects of the sampling of hydrogen at heavy-duty hydrogen refuelling stations for purity assessment, with a focus on the current and future specifications and operations at HD-HRS. This study describes the state-of-the art of sampling systems currently under development for use at HD-HRS and highlights a number of aspects which must be taken into consideration to ensure safe and accurate sampling: risk assessment for the whole sampling exercise, selection of cylinders, methods to prepare cylinders before the sampling, filling pressure, and venting of the sampling systems.

1. Introduction

Europe aims to be climate neutral by 2050 (long-term strategy, 2050). The European Parliament endorsed the net-zero greenhouse gas emissions objective in its resolution on climate change in March 2019 and resolution on the European Green Deal in January 2020. To achieve the climate change targets set for 2050 in the European Green Deal (A European Green Deal, 2019), realistic technological solutions must be further developed, and this development and subsequent uptake must be facilitated by policies and laws. In 2013, EU defined a policy called the Trans-European Transport Network policy (TEN-T) based on Regulation (EU) No 1315/2013 which supported a large number of projects aiming at facilitation transports (goods and passengers) within the EU. This

regulation is currently being revised in order to for example, make the network greener as required by the European Green Deal and the Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy. Whilst it is difficult to predict the supply mechanism for energy, the electricity grid alone can most probably not support the energy demands of the users. According to the 'Hydrogen Roadmap Europe' (FCH JU) (Hydrogen Roadmap Europe) in the 2019 report, Europe will potentially be able to generate approximately 2250 terawatt hours (TWh) of electricity from hydrogen in Europe in 2050 which represents roughly a quarter of the EU's total energy demand' (Hydrogen Roadmap Europe). Therefore, increasing attention is being paid to the role of hydrogen in the transition to a sustainable energy system.

Very recently, the European Parliament and the Council reached an

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: karine.arrhenius@ri.se (K. Arrhenius).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2024.09.032>

Received 27 March 2024; Received in revised form 10 July 2024; Accepted 15 September 2024

Available online 23 September 2024

2352-4847/© 2024 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

agreement to boost the number of publicly accessible hydrogen refuelling stations (and electric recharging stations) strategically placed across the EU's main transport corridors and hubs. The new regulation for the deployment of alternative fuels infrastructure (AFIR) (European Green Deal, 2023) sets targets for electric recharging and hydrogen refuelling infrastructure for the road sector. According to this law, the following target will have to be met in 2025 or 2030: hydrogen refuelling infrastructure for both cars and trucks must be deployed in order to allow hydrogen vehicles to travel across the EU (specific targets: all urban nodes and every 200 km along the TEN-T core network). To that end, Member States shall ensure that by December 31, 2030, publicly accessible hydrogen refuelling stations designed for a minimum cumulative capacity of 1 tonne per day and equipped with at least a 700 bar dispenser are deployed along the TEN-T core network.

Heavy-duty- transport is one of the main pillars of the hydrogen industry, which will be used to support the transition to zero emission transport in Europe by 2050. Hydrogen fuel allows for longer distances with less refuelling compared to electric vehicles based on batteries, so it is ideal for fuelling heavy-duty- trucks and trailers, and public transit buses (DOE), which travel hundreds of kilometres at a time.

The first hydrogen fuel-cell electric heavy-duty vehicles are already being rolled out in Europe. From the mid-2020s on, at least 60,000 trucks expected to be in operation by 2030. To encourage this development, the most important consideration factors are (Overview Hydrogen Refuelling For Heavy Duty Vehicles, 2021):

- Convenient refuelling times of some minutes (in comparison, an LNG truck takes around 7 minutes to refuel (JEC Tank-To-Wheels report v5, 2020));
- Payload (including the weight of hydrogen, the storage tanks and accessories for the storage solution);
- Operation range (today's long-haul HDV can travel more than 1000 km without refuelling. With an average consumption of between 7 and 8 kg H₂ per 100 km for HDV, a minimum of 40 kg of onboard H₂ storage is required);
- Costs.

A large infrastructure comprising truck-suitable hydrogen refuelling stations will then soon be required. According to the ACEA (European Automobile Manufacturers Association) (Interactive map, 2030), a target of around 300 hydrogen refuelling stations for trucks by 2025, and at least 1000 by 2030, should be set. In 2021, there were 144 hydrogen refuelling stations (HRS) in operation in the EU, the majority in Germany, France, Denmark, the Netherlands and Belgium (ACEA, 2023), only 16 delivering 350 bar H₂ to HDVs, mainly city buses.

According to stakeholders who answered a questionnaire produced as part of MethHyTrucks project, many challenges arise before this infrastructure is in place and many efforts are needed including a strong political support. Among others, technical readiness of equipment is often mentioned, in particular, the availability of adapted equipment (e.g., new design nozzles and receptacles), the development/availability of advanced communications systems able to perform well at higher flows, and availability of refuelling protocols.

The lack of supply chain providers and the lack of alignment between players, including the “chicken and egg” problematic for stations (ability to build quickly and efficiently a network of stations) and vehicles have also been mentioned as challenges to overcome.

Hydrogen-powered vehicles require pure hydrogen (>99.97 vol%) as some contaminants can reduce the performance of the fuel cell even at very low levels (e.g. H₂O and O₂ below 5 ppm and N₂ below 300 ppm) while some contaminants e.g. water affect the balance of the plant. Sampling systems and methods have already been developed for use at hydrogen refuelling stations (HRS) for light-duty (LD) vehicles, however, there is a lack of technical evidence for heavy-duty transport. Despite the knowledge that has been gathered on the durability of light-duty fuel cell electrical vehicles, the challenge increases for the heavy-

duty application as heavy-duty vehicles need to have a longer lifetime, better durability, and reliable performance, and as the HD-HRS network will be shared between operators. Sampling should not create a source of discrepancies in quality within the emerging network.

This study reviews different aspects of the sampling of hydrogen at heavy-duty refuelling stations for purity assessment and discusses other aspects such as current and future specifications and operation of HD-HRS that may affect hydrogen purity assessment. With the foreseen development of a large infrastructure comprising truck-suitable hydrogen refuelling stations and vehicles, new or adapted sampling approaches, for HD-HRS applications, will need to be trialed in real conditions to assess the performance of the sampling approach to collect a representative sample of hydrogen at these emerging stations.

2. Operational parameters at HD-HRS

Europe's future hydrogen refuelling infrastructure will need to meet expected demand; by covering important transport corridors and locating close to logistic and distribution centers (Overview Hydrogen Refuelling For Heavy Duty Vehicles, 2021). A possible barrier to the deployment of refuelling stations is the land area they require, which can be a constraint in dense urban areas where space for stations is limited (Department for Structural and Cohesion Policies, 2021).

For future developments, the amount of hydrogen stored at the HRS is crucial for HD application. In the report “Overview Hydrogen Refuelling For Heavy Duty Vehicles” (Overview Hydrogen Refuelling For Heavy Duty Vehicles, 2021), stations are classified by size depending on the maximum hydrogen throughput per day: small stations (S) having a throughput of 200 kg, medium (M) of 500 kg, large (L) of 1000 kg and extra-large (2XL) of 4000 kg. Hydrogen is either delivered to the HRS or generated onsite. Another supply option is the use of liquid organic hydrogen carriers (LOHC) which are organic compounds that can absorb and release hydrogen through chemical reactions and can therefore be used to store hydrogen. Hydrogen is delivered in either gaseous or liquid form using gaseous tube trailers (compressed gas, CGH₂) or cryogenic liquid tanker trucks (liquid H₂, LH₂), the later having 10 times the capacity of the former. Gaseous hydrogen can also be transported through pipelines.

Using the information found in the report “Overview Hydrogen Refuelling For Heavy Duty Vehicles”, Table 1 summarizes the operational parameters of HD-HRS for different supply options:

3. Refuelling protocols

A refuelling protocol is a set of procedures that dictate the process that a station follows to safely fuel a hydrogen storage system (Ehrhart et al., 2020). Due to the characteristics of hydrogen and the limits of storage systems, refueling protocols are developed to:

- Ensure a complete hydrogen fill (typical state of charge range: 90–100 % without overfilling);
- Ensure that the hydrogen storage system stays within its operational boundaries (pressure and temperature) and does not exceed storage safety limits (for example, a maximum gas temperature of 85°C and maximum pressure of 875 bar);
- Meet the target in terms of fueling time (for example, the US DOE FCEV target for 2017 is 3.3 min with 5 kg H₂ storage).

Currently, the majority of HRS are built for light-duty vehicles and typically use as fuelling protocol, the SAE J2601 standard which describes H35-H70 precooled refuelling (Mathison, 2021), or the Clean Energy Partnership (CEP) protocol(s) (SAE, 2016). CEP (Clean Energy Partnership) teamed up with Wenger Engineering to develop a look-up table refuelling protocol approach for busses and trucks (Clean Energy Partnership, 023) The protocol is defined for tank system sizes from 20 to 42.5 kg at 350 bar. These protocols are more suitable for the storage

Table 1
Operational parameters at HD-HRS(Overview Hydrogen Refuelling For Heavy Duty Vehicles, 2021).

Supply option	CGH ₂ , LH ₂	CGH ₂ , LH ₂	LH ₂	LH ₂ (CGH ₂ feasible)
HRS specifications				
Main components	H ₂ storage, compressor or cryo pump, cooling unit (if CGH ₂), dispenser (nozzle, hose)	H ₂ storage, compressor or cryo pump, cooling unit (if CGH ₂), dispenser (nozzle, hose)	H ₂ storage, subcooled liquid H ₂ pump, dispenser (nozzle, hose)	LH ₂ storage, cryo pump, dispenser (nozzle, hose)
H ₂ storage type	Depending on specification either: trailer swap, supply storage, pipeline	Depending on specification either: trailer swap, supply storage, pipeline	Depending on specification either: trailer swap, supply storage	Depending on specification either: trailer swap, supply storage
Refuelling pressure	350 bar	700 bar	Approx. 16 bar	300 bar
Ease of expanding to 700 bar passenger vehicles refuelling	Complex and costly integration due to higher compressor ratio and cooling demand	Relatively simple expandability due to existing technology and lower performance requirements	Complex and costly integration of additional high pressure cryo pump system, nozzle, hose etc	Complex and costly integration of additional high pressure cryo pump system, nozzle, hose etc
Data communication between HRS and vehicle	Necessary for better performance	Necessary for better performance	Not required	Not required
Targeted max flow rate	300 g/s	300 g/s	110–140 g/s (per pump)	55–220 g/s per pump
Vehicle specifications				
H ₂ tank pressure (MAWP*)	350 (437.5 bar)	700 (875 bar)	Approx. 5–16 bar	≤ 300 bar
VH ₂ tank temperature	−40–85 °C	−40–85 °C	−248 to −245 °C	Approx. −240 °C to −150 °C
Storage capacity	Today <42.5 kg (intended > 42.5 kg)	Up to 100 kg	>80 kg	> 80 kg

* MAWP: Maximum allowable working pressure

capacities relevant for medium- and heavy-duty vehicles. It is worth mentioning that HRS manufacturers can implement “home-made” protocols that could be validated and approved during the metrological type-approval tests of the HRS, but implementing the well-known protocols stated earlier could grant access to the H2Live database and be implemented in the GPS of the hydrogen cars if the CEP Site Acceptance Tests (SAT) are validated.

To fulfil future refuelling needs (for example, a 100 kg HD truck storage system refuelled in 10 min), a refuelling point should reach a mean fuelling rate of approximately 170 g/s with a peak fuelling rate up to 300 g/s (Technical report, 2021) which is a larger flow than in the current available protocols /SAE J2601–1, 60 g/s or SAE J2601–2, 120 g/s.

Currently, different vehicle-to-station interface strategies exist. For example, the vehicle can provide tank parameters through an electrical interface (called “communication”, which is an infrared communication defined by SAE J2799:201 (Horizon Europe, 2023), or the vehicle can only provide the pressure in the tank (called “non-communication”). All existing protocols use communication between vehicle tank system and HRS only before refuelling. This leads to conservative protocols with low performance in refuelling time, as lot of restrictive assumptions have to be made. To ensure the best refuelling performances, reliabilities and costs for a broad range of possible storage capacities and configurations for heavy-duty vehicles, new refuelling protocols should be developed and implemented. Future new performance-orientated approaches such as the SAE J2601–5 (SAE J2799, 2019) will allow vehicle specific information to be communicated to the station before and during the refuelling. However, these imply higher security requirements for communication between tank system and the HRS. If an advanced and safe communication between the vehicle and the stations is achieved, this will lead to a change in responsibility for the refuelling process – the manufacturer has to provide the correct data set for the station to process. Together with the actual parameters regarding tank pressure and ambient temperature, the suitable refuelling protocol can be applied.

The refuelling process is standardised. SAE J2601 (Mathison, 2021) provides protocols and process limits for hydrogen refuelling of light-duty vehicles (flow rates up to 60 g/s) and SAE J2601/2 (SAE, 2022) for heavy-duty vehicles (flow rates up to 120 g/s). Compliance with this standard ensures fast and safe refuelling. SAE J2601 describes two different methods. The first method is based on the classic look-up table (L/T) approach, which specifies an average pressure ramp rate (APRR) for refuelling. The other approach is a fast fill protocol, MC Default fill, which is based on dynamic pressure ramp rates (DPRR) that are continuously calculated during the fuelling process. Here, M stands

for the mass and C for the specific heat capacity as key values in a heat transfer equation. The result of this calculation is a fill time optimised for the ambient conditions at the HRS. Both approaches have been developed using thermodynamic modelling and simulation. In addition, both methods allow refuelling with or without communication, as specified in SAE J2799 (Horizon Europe, 2023). The L/T approach takes into account the station type (station pressure and dispensing temperature), ambient temperature, compressed hydrogen storage system (CHSS) capacity category, and CHSS outlet pressure to determine the APRR and refuelling target pressure. The Formula-based MC method works in a similar way to the L/T method, with some significant differences that should lead to an improvement in refuelling times. This method is a representation of the heat capacity of the CHSS. The method is an analytical approach to calculating the amount of heat generated during refuelling. The approach allows for an accurate determination of the gas temperature at the end of the refuelling process. The actual pre-cooling temperature is used as the input parameter for the calculation and not the limit temperature of the station type (e.g. T40) as in the L/T method. Unlike the L/T method, the MC method calculates a DPRR with dynamic feedback and control based on the measurement of pressure and temperature at the dispenser. The target pressures are calculated continuously and dynamically to optimise filling and minimise refuelling time. At the same time, a limit pressure is calculated that takes precedence over the communication target pressure to ensure that the CHSS remains within its operating limits. The MC Formula-based protocol uses fixed parameters only for the first 30 s of the refuelling process, after which the parameters are updated every second until the refuelling process is complete.

Several research projects have worked on developing protocols for HD conditions. The ongoing EU-funded RHeadHy project (SAE International, 2023) has some goal to develop high flow refuelling components and refuelling line, in order to implement and test new protocols to allow refuelling of 700 bar H₂ trucks at 100 kg within 10 min. EU-funded project PRHYDE (Refuelling Heavy Duty with very High flow Hydrogen, 2024) aimed to develop recommendations for a non-proprietary HD refuelling protocol used for future standardization activities and concluded that more work is needed in this area, using both different models and practical experiments.

The PRHYDE project has developed a feature called “SOC Taper” to adjust the refuelling rate when the refuelling station encounters non-ideal situations such as low storage capacity or high flow restrictions. This is an approach that reduces the pressure ramp rate as necessary to achieve the target SOC. SOC Taper is not a stand-alone refuelling concept. The protocol developed by ISO/TC 197 WG24 (SAE J2799,

2019) is based in particular on feedback from the PRHYDE project and on the MC Formula-based refuelling protocol MCF-HF-G (MC Formula - High Flow – General) in SAE TIR J2601–5 (flow rates up to 300 g/s). TIR J2601–5 is independent from SAE J2601–2.

4. Hydrogen purity

Hydrogen-powered vehicles require pure hydrogen (>99.7 vol%) as some contaminants can reduce the performance of the fuel cell even if present in the hydrogen at very low levels. The purity of the hydrogen dispensed at hydrogen refuelling points should comply with the technical specifications included in the ISO 14687 (PRHYDE, 2020), EN 17124 (Geneva, Switzerland: International Standardization Organization, 2019), and SAE J2719:202003 (EN 17124, 2022) standards. The quality of the hydrogen can be controlled either onsite using online monitoring or after spot sampling and transport to a laboratory for offline analysis (J2719_202003, 2020; ISO 19880–8:2019, 2019).

Spot sampling implies collecting a specific amount of gas in appropriate vessels. The biggest challenge with this method is the sample integrity, namely selecting a vessel in which the concentration of every impurity present alone or together with others will remain stable from the time the gas is sampled to the time the gas is analysed without any loss occurring at any time.

Typically, samples of hydrogen containing inert gases and other non-reactive components (e.g., carbon monoxide) at the levels specified in ISO 14687 are expected to remain stable in cylinders or other vessel types (ISO 21087:2019, 2019). On the other hand, samples that contain impurities classified as reactive, in particular those that only allowed in the hydrogen at very low trace levels because of their poisoning effect on the fuel cell catalyst or membrane, are expected to be unstable in time. In a recent review of different sampling strategies, an attempt to produce a table of material compatibility was done (Table 2 from (CCQM-K164, 2021)). However, the authors pointed out the lack of data obtained in a hydrogen matrix and the lack of standardization of parameters in the studies performed to assess the stability of components in each cylinder (e.g. study time or lack of important information such as the filling pressure). Even the definition of the term “suitable” would need to be defined quantitatively.

Typically for gas standards in cylinders, synthetic gas mixtures of known fractions of impurities in hydrogen, stabilities of 6 months up to 5 years are specified. They mainly depend on factors like the amount fractions, the reactivity of the component and if it is a binary or multi-component gas standard. For H₂ samples, a stability period of about 3–4 months would typically be sufficient as samples are normally analysed shortly after being taken.

The period of stability of hydrogen samples should be in compliance with the requirements set in the ISO 21087:

“The relative combined measurement uncertainty for that concentration should be below 10 % of the concentration generally. An exception could be accepted for an amount fraction equal or below 10 nmol/mol. In these cases, a higher relative combined standard measurement uncertainty could be accepted but should not be higher than 50 % of the amount fraction”

Table 2
Sampling devices characteristics.

Devices	ENGIE device	HySaM	NPL DirSam	HD-ParSam	Airborne
Sampling strategy	Serial	Parallel	Serial	Parallel	Serial
Pressure (bar)	350	350/700	350	350	350
Max flow (g/s)	120	120	120	120	120
Sampling cylinder	Two-ended valve stainless steel sulfinit coated cylinder of 1 L	One-ended valve cylinders of 2.25-L or 10-L (3 cylinders can be sampled at the same occasion)	One-ended valve 10 L aluminum cylinder with DIN 477/1 valve	One-ended valve 10 L aluminum cylinder with DIN 477/1 valve	Two-ended valve 1 L Silconert passivated cylinders

It can be therefore derived that, for all compounds except total sulfur, the stability must be better than 20 % (preferably about 10 % as other sources also contribute to the uncertainty of the measurements). For sulfurs, a much higher instability is allowed. It must be maximum 100 %, but preferably below 50 %.

To complete the material compatibility table from (CCQM-K164, 2021), new data were produced during the project 19ENG04 MetroHyVe2 (Arrhenius et al., 2021) and a new compatibility table can be found in the good practice guide on selection of sampling vessels for hydrogen purity testing (EURAMET, 2019–2023).

First and foremost, suitability of the cylinder's treatment must be established for compounds present individually in the gas: recent studies (EURAMET, 2019–2023) have shown that DB Gold and Sulfinit stainless steel were the most suitable cylinders but even these are not suitable for all gaseous components to analyse for hydrogen purity, a combination of at least two cylinder types may be necessary. The most challenging compounds are sulfur compounds (at least hydrogen sulphide and carbonyl sulphide) but some issues have been also observed with hydrogen chloride, ammonia, formic acid and formaldehyde.

Suitability of the treatment to avoid interactions between compounds should then be studied: the presence of some compounds may stabilize other compounds (such as water for formic acid and formaldehyde), the presence of some compounds may lead to cross-interactions. However, these effects are not always related to the cylinder itself, but sometimes only to the compounds; the results of studies performed on multiple compounds in the cylinder showed that interactions between contaminants in the same cylinder are possible but limited to ammonia, formaldehyde, and formic acid. Such cross reactivity and potential by-products need to be understood and differentiated from stability issues.

Besides the material compatibility of the impurity in contact with the vessel, there are other factors that influence the stability of the analytes and their analyzed amount fraction in the H₂ samples. Among them, the sample pressure. For components which adsorb on the cylinder wall, a pressure dependence is expected (Morris et al., 2023) It is assumed that a fixed number of molecules are required to occupy the active sites on the inner surface of the cylinder. Filling the sampling container at a higher pressure will typically lead to relatively lower losses and hence to a better estimate of the contamination level of HRS. At lower pressure, this would be a larger proportion of the total number of molecules available compared to higher pressure. Some of the components tend to desorb again when the pressure in the sampling container gets less than ~10 bar (Morris et al., 2023).

As long as the effect of the filling pressure has not been studied more extensively, stability studies shall be performed at pressures similar to the ones used in the sampling strategies (not less than 70 bar and up to 150 bar).

Studies performed during the MetroHyVe2 project have shown that a preselection of cylinders may be needed for some impurities as it has been shown that oxygen decay occurred at different rates within cylinders of the same internal treatment). Decrease in treatment/cylinder's performance have been shown over time but the lifetime of cylinder

passivation types for hydrogen fuel sampling requires further investigation.

5. Sampling strategies

The key aspects of the different strategies for sampling hydrogen at the nozzle for light-duty vehicles for offline analysis were summarized in a recent review article (CCQM-K164, 2021). Sampling strategies used at HD stations can be similar to the ones developed for LD HRS as long as the sampling devices are adapted to the HD conditions. Another review focused on sampling and analysis of particulate matter in hydrogen fuel (Leuenberger et al., 2015). Two different types of strategies were defined in (CCQM-K164, 2021): “gas parallel” and “gas serial”. In the “Gas serial” strategies, the sample is taken directly into a sampling cylinder. These sampling systems imply controlling the conditions and may require operating the HRS in service mode. The sampling system may also include a tank allowing to not override the protocol of the station. At least four different strategies are based on this principle. One of these strategies is described in the standard ASTM D7606–17 (Aarhaug et al., 2023a) and two other strategies have been developed by Air Liquide and ENGIE. The fourth strategy is the method currently used in Japan which is summarised in ISO19880–1, Annex K (ASTM D7606–7, 2017).

The “Gas parallel” strategies do not require to bypass the safety protocol of the station as a tee-connection is used to parallelly fill the sampling cylinder and a FCEV or a receptacle (larger than the sampling cylinder). At least two different sampling strategies are based on this principle, one strategy using the Linde Qualitizer and one strategy using a device called Hy-SaM developed by ZBT and ZSW. Sampling devices with the Linde Qualitizer are used by several organisations who then adopt different sampling strategies (for example, slightly different types of cylinders with regards to the internal treatment or different protocols to prepare the cylinders and with or without methods to purge the sampling device).

All the strategies use sampling lines in stainless steel however it is not always clear if specific treatments are applied to the sampling systems. Influence of components such as pressure regulators and pressure gauges have not been sufficiently studied to determine if they may lead to biased analyses results due to adsorption happening inside.

All strategies imply a cleaning procedure of the cylinders and a sampling procedure involving purging to avoid false positive contamination which effectiveness has been assessed more or less extensively. Such methods have been developed and tested during the project MetroHyVe1 (ISO, 2020a) and presented in the report A4.1.7 “Good practice guide on effective sampling and transportation of hydrogen from the refuelling station as required by ISO14687”; a method using purging cycles and a method using turbo evacuation.

The sampling systems use a large variety of gas cylinders with respect to material (stainless steel, manganese steel or aluminum), size, passivation and valve type. The rationale behind the cylinder’s selection is often not specified. Due to the filling pressure (all above 60 bar and up to 150 bar), the quantity of gas sampled is at minimum 35 liters (ASTM D7606, 0.5 L cylinder filled with 69 bar) and up to 750 liters (Air Liquide strategy).

6. Sampling devices for HD-HRS

The sampling of hydrogen fuel at a HRS is an operation within an explosive atmosphere (ATEX) area involving safety risks, which include a venting step. The sampling exercise is not part of the normal procedure that occurs at a HRS. As HD-HRS operate at high flowrates and downtime has to be minimised (to reduce the impact on the refuelling of trucks), safety is a key element for the standardisation of sampling.

Sampling methods addressed in ISO 19880–1 Annex K (ASTM D7606–7, 2017) have been developed for light-duty HRS and need to be adapted and validated for heavy-duty HRS. Sampling devices

technologies need to be upgraded to address the refuelling needs of heavy-duty vehicles.

Several strategies developers are in the process of adapting their devices for HD conditions to sample hydrogen for offline analysis.

The ENGIE device (Fig. 1) has been fitted with a receptacle compatible with a 350 barg HDV nozzle and no modification of the device for pressure or flow was required. Indeed, the device was originally designed and qualified to support pressure up to 875 barg and, the tank volume of the ENGIE’s device of 55 L and the valves could originally support flow rate up to 120 g/s.

Sampling device and tank are designed to be used from -40 to $+80^{\circ}\text{C}$ which implies that sampling protocols needs to ensure that the temperature of hydrogen will be between these limits.

ENGIE brings their own venting mast on-site for the sampling. It consists of a stainless-steel mast of 3 m height connected to the sampling device through a 10 m stainless steel flexible hose. This solution allows to safely vent hydrogen contained into the tank after the sampling. The tank is PED (pressure equipment directive (EURAMET, 2017–2020)) certified and need to be inerted before transport. This step could be eliminated by using instead a TPED (transport pressure equipment directive (Directive, 2014)) tank. As the smallest tank volume implemented in the table of the HDV 350 barg HF filling protocols (CEP/WENGER) is around 835 liters, the current volume of the tank does not allow the station to deliver hydrogen without by-passing the safety protocol. New protocols are in preparation and will, maybe, include tank volume around 420 L. To be able to sample without by-passing the safety protocol, the volume of the tank must be increased and to that effect, the whole bench must be redesigned in order to get enough space to fit this significantly larger tank.

The Hy-SaM device (Fig. 2) has originally been developed to sample from 700 bar refuelling stations. In conformity to SAE, it is pressure-resistant up to 875 bar. The system is divided into three modules.

Fig. 1. Engie device.

Fig. 2. The Hy-SaM device.

Module 1 contains all parts for simultaneously sampling up to three cylinders (2.25 or 10 liters). Module 2 is the mobile vent. Module 3 contains a 76-liter buffer tank including the necessary safety components. By using module 3, sampling can be performed without refuelling an FCEV by using the buffer tank as a sink. Optionally, the vent lines (including safety relief valves) from modules 1 and 3 can be connected to module 2 or directly to the HRS vent line. Also optional is the simultaneous sampling for particles with the HYDAC PSA system. To adapt the system to HD-HRS, a new line will be added for sampling at 350 bar. This hardware is suitable for minimum hydrogen temperatures of $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (nozzle temperature limit). With the new design, it will be possible to sample from 700 bar and 350 bar refuelling lines with only one sampling device.

A second 350 bar high flow line with receptacle and high flow nozzle is being added to the Hy-SaM device to accommodate sampling at HD HRS (350 bar). The sizes of the new pipings have also been increased to support high flow (up to 120 g/s). An added switch valve can be used to direct the gas into the correct pressure line (350 or 700 bar). While performing a parallel sampling (e.g. with a FCEV), the new device is compatible with all protocols for HD up to 120 g/s. The device does not need to be modified for the venting operations.

Both HySaM fueling lines (350 bar HF and 700 bar LD) use the same sampling line and therefore allow to fill up to three sample cylinders to 850 bar continuously during a fueling, without the necessary of overriding the fueling protocol of the HRS. The maximum flow for the sample is restricted by an orifice.

Airborne Labs International have developed their sampling system based on ASTM D7606. The design of the NSP-7606 targeted a maximum flow of 125 g/s. Samples are collected in 1 L Silconert passivated cylinders. Adaptation for heavy duty requires a change of receptacle and potentially, a change of vent stack to one with larger tubing inner dimensions. Airborne Labs International sampler MRM

7650 was designed for 125 g/s flows, changing the receptacle to a heavy duty compatible one, would allow for HD sampling. The SS filter holder fixes 47 mm filters. A totalizer is used to assess the amount of hydrogen dispensed over the filter. It will also report dynamically the flow over the filter. As for their gas sampling counterpart, the vent stack may possibly be exchanged for one with bigger tube inner dimensions.

Discussions with HYDAC regarding adaptation of their PSA-H70 particulate sampler have revealed that the initial design was for 120 g/s flow. This means that by replacing the nozzle and receptacle of the device, the device should be compatible with heavy-duty particulate sampling. For their MK2 version of the device, depressurization will not be possible on a H35 nozzle since it was designed for H70 depressurization.

Within a NPL internal project, two new sampling systems have been developed for HD applications. The first follows a direct sampling strategy as described in the standard ASTM D7606–17 (Aarhaug et al., 2023a). The sampling is performed at the nozzle and the venting of hydrogen into the atmosphere is performed through an exhaust stack. The sampling device is referred to as the NPL Hydrogen direct sampling apparatus (NPL DirSam, Fig. 3). The method is adaptable for stations delivering hydrogen fuel both at 350 and 700 bar and is capable of up to 120 g/s (high flow). It comes with a 5-m flexible line connected to a tripod foot. The flow to the cylinders is adjustable using a flow metering valve. The cylinder for sampling is a 10 L aluminum cylinder with DIN 477/1 valve. The second system follows a parallel sampling strategy. The new system developed is a sampling device called HD-ParSam which allows sampling according to the ISO19880–1 and SAE J2601 without overriding the refuelling protocol. It also offers the possibility of purging and venting to the atmosphere with its own sampling vent. The method is adaptable for stations delivering hydrogen fuel both at 350 and 700 bar and is capable of up to 120 g/s (high flow). The system will be completed and delivered to NPL in early 2024.

The advantage of the direct sampling strategies used in Asia and in the US, is the fact that the sampling doesn't require to follow any filling protocol. The HRS is set in maintenance mode and therefore pressure and flow can be adjusted to filling the sampling container. In such realisation, the evolution from LD to HD may require only adaptation of the receptacle and high-pressure section up to the pressure safety valve to follow the HRS requirements. Therefore, the transition from LD direct sampling to HD direct sampling can easily be done through a careful management of the HRS parameters in maintenance mode.

Another important aspect of the sampling is the safe venting of the skid or the sample at the end of the analysis. Several parameters (internal or external) can describe the venting of the sampling system:

- The exhaust line must withstand the pressure in the vicinity of the valve where it could be up to 87.5 MPa.
- The exhaust line must have an appropriate inner diameter to reduce the velocity and the potential radiated acoustic pressure. It could be remembered that the acoustic power is related to the velocity (see Lighthill analogy (European Directive, 2010)).
- The final exhaust piping design and shape can be adapted to improve the noise radiation and its directivity. It is recommended that the jet exhaust goes upward to reduce the potential undesired wind effect that pushes the hydrogen jet back towards the operator on the ground.
- The height is obviously an important criterion that need to be defined. It is usual to see venting lines around 4 m height. The ATEX zoning guides the height of the venting stack. The zoning is usually described at zone 1 during the venting.
- Another feature that can be implemented is one or multiple calibrated orifices to get a fixed mass flow rate.
- The location of the staff performing the venting is important to avoid any potential migration of the hydrogen towards them.

Some of the characteristics of the sampling devices presented here

Fig. 3. The DirSam device.

are summarised in the [Table 2](#).

7. Influence of HRS parameters on sampling

Another aspect important to consider when sampling hydrogen at HD-HRS is the potential impact that the operational parameters prevailing at the station may have on the sample itself. The filling protocol will realise the optimum filling of the FCEV using the different available storage banks (related to pressure, volume). Therefore, each FCEV filling may involve different storage banks. An assumption that all storage banks contain the same hydrogen quality is therefore made. However, it may not be always correct especially with complex stations. Some tests performed during MetroHyVe2 project have shown that the quality of the hydrogen can vary from storage banks within the same HRS. Hydrogen was collected from different storage banks and analysed with regards to nitrogen, water, carbon dioxide and oxygen. The results showed that the quality of hydrogen varied in the different storage banks by a factor up to seven for the amount fraction of carbon dioxide, up to four for the amount fraction of water and a factor up to two for the amount fraction of nitrogen ([Lighthill et al., 1107](#)). Even if the stations used for these tests is a research facility, consideration regarding the number of storage banks and the complexity of the HRS may be relevant recording. Further research is needed to define how sampling should be realized in correlation with the number of storage banks (i.e., all storage banks sampled evenly).

The precooling temperature is another parameter relevant during a sampling. For the direct sampling method, the HRS is in maintenance mode, and therefore the precooling temperature, pressure and flow rate may be fixed by the operators. Currently there is little knowledge on the influence of these parameters on the sampling results. The heat exchanger may influence the water amount fraction in the hydrogen gas delivered, for example, precooling at -20°C may lead to water accumulation in the heat exchanger, while no precooling may lead to a higher water amount fraction as no trapping in the heat exchanger may happen.

Another experiment performed during MetroHyVe2 has demonstrated that hydrogen samples didn't originate from the same storage bank, even if several samplings with different sampling systems were performed consecutively ([Lighthill et al., 1107](#)). Therefore, consecutive samplings may not lead to obtaining the same sample.

8. Uncertainty contribution

When estimating the measurement uncertainty of a value obtained for the quality assessment of hydrogen, sampling contributes to the total uncertainty budget. The calculation of this contribution is however quite complex and applies both to LD and HD conditions. One important document regarding the measurement uncertainty arising from sampling is the Eurachem/EUROLAB/CITAC/Nordtest Guide on this topic ([Aarhaug et al., 2023b](#)). The aim of this guide is to detail and explain the methods available for the estimation of uncertainty that include the contribution from sampling.

There are two main approaches to uncertainty estimation arising from sampling described in this guide, (these methods also apply to any measurement):

- 1) The empirical approach (also called experimental, retrospective or top down) which is widely applicable (e.g., gaseous, liquid and solid).
- 2) The modelling approach (also called theoretical, predictive of bottom up) which is used in particular situations (e.g., particulate solids).

The empirical approach relies on repetitive realisation and on the variance observed in real sampling. It does not provide any information on the exact technical source of the uncertainty (i.e., issues with heterogeneity or pressure). Therefore, it is difficult to resolve or improve the uncertainty due to the lack of knowledge on the real sources of it.

There are four sources contributing to the uncertainty:

- 1) Random errors arising from the sampling (called sampling precision)
- 2) Random errors arising from the analysis (called analytical precision)
- 3) Systematic errors arising from the sampling (called sampling bias)
- 4) Systematic errors arising from the analysis (called analytical bias)

The duplicates method is the simplest and probably most cost-effective of the four methods existing to estimate sampling uncertainty using the empirical approach. It is based upon a single person taking a small proportion (e.g., 10 %, but no less than eight samples) of the primary samples in duplicate (by repeating the same nominal sampling protocol). Ideally the duplicates are taken from at least eight sampling targets. If not possible, then all eight duplicates can be taken from one target, but in that case, the uncertainty will only be applicable to this

target. Each duplicate is analysed twice. This system of duplicated sampling and chemical analysis is known as a “balanced design”.

The modelling approach identifies and quantifies all the sources of uncertainty, and then combines those as a budget to give an estimate of the combined standard uncertainty, which is calculated by summing the uncertainty from all of the steps using a model that adds the variances.

For gas sampling, attention should be paid to but not limited to the following technical aspects in order to collect a sufficient representative sample (Eurachem/EUROLAB/CITAC/Nordtest Guide, 2006).

- Adsorption, reaction and permeation of the sampling system
- Leaks and atmospheric diffusion in the sampling system
- Purging of the sampling system
- Homogeneity of gas

In any case, the validation of a sampling system is often complex compared to the validation of analytical methods, for which validation parameters can be obtained through measurements of real samples and reference materials. Sampling reference materials are extremely complex to prepare (i.e., accurately contaminating the whole hydrogen of a refuelling station to verify the ability of a system to collect a representative sample). Therefore, the application of the empirical or duplicate approach will be preferably based on repeated measurements in real conditions. However, due to the absence of contaminants in the hydrogen (hydrogen dispensed has been found in most of the cases to contain very few compounds above the thresholds in the quality standards), the methods will therefore only give information about the few compound(s) present above the limit of detection of the analytical methods.

Another approach would be to simulate a sampling event (or an event close to a refuelling event) using reference gas cylinders with known amount fraction of contaminants which allows to study of more contaminants including reactive species that are not found in real hydrogen samples. However, such realisation may be limited by difficulties in simulating refilling conditions (T, P, flow). So, these types of tests would mostly provide insights on the ability of the systems to correctly sample the compounds.

Applying the same approach used in inter-laboratory comparisons would allow to achieve a consensus value for all compounds sampled and provide equivalence between sampling systems. This approach has been applied with some success in 19ENG04 MetroHyVe 2 for light-duty sampling at HRS for four sampling systems (Lighthill et al., 1107).

9. Conclusions

This study reviews different aspects of the sampling of hydrogen at heavy-duty refuelling stations for purity assessment and discusses other aspects that may affect hydrogen purity assessment such as current and future specifications and operational parameters at the HD-HRS. With the foreseen development of a large infrastructure comprising truck-suitable hydrogen refuelling stations and vehicles, a lot of efforts must be made to enable the safe and efficient utilisation of hydrogen. The majority of HRS built for light-duty vehicles use the SAE J2601 standard or the Clean Energy Partnership (CEP) protocol(s) which are typically unsuitable for the storage systems capacities used for medium and heavy-duty vehicles. To fulfil future refuelling needs (for example 100 kg HD truck storage system refuelled in 10 min), a refuelling point should reach a mean fuelling rate of approximately 170 g/s with a peak fuelling rate up to 300 g/s. To allow assessment of hydrogen purity, new or adapted sampling approaches, for HD-HRS applications, will need to be trialed in real conditions. These approaches need to be tested to assess their capability to collect a representative sample of hydrogen at these emerging stations. Many aspects need to be taken into consideration: risk assessment for the whole sampling exercise, selection of the cylinder, method to prepare the cylinder before the sampling, filling pressure, venting of the sampling systems, every step must be done to ensure safe

and accurate sampling. Even the influence of the parameters at the station (e.g., pressure, flow rate and flow rate variation) need to be studied.

The project MetHyTrucks aims at delivering the evidence needed to support the standardisation of hydrogen fuel sampling for heavy-duty applications. During the project MetHyTrucks, several sampling systems will be developed and trialed in order to assess their performances. The project will also develop protocols to validate sampling systems and to estimate the uncertainty budget associated with sampling. However, the validation of a sampling system is complex as sampling reference materials are extremely complex to prepare, the application of any approach to estimate uncertainty will be preferably based on repeated measurements in real conditions. The absence of contaminants in the hydrogen dispensed in most of the HRSs complicates the use of classical methods to validate the sampling systems and only the simulation of a sampling event using reference gas cylinders with known amount fraction of contaminants will allow to study reactive species which are not found in a typical real hydrogen sample.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Karine Arrhenius: Writing – original draft. **Thomas Bacquart:** Writing – review & editing. **Thor Anders Aarhaug:** Writing – review & editing. **Sven Kaiser:** Writing – review & editing. **Maxime Dufond:** Writing – review & editing. **Quentin Nouvelot:** Writing – review & editing. **Remy Maury:** Writing – review & editing. **Stefan Persijn:** Writing – review & editing. **Oliver Bükker:** Methodology. **Danique van Workum:** Writing – review & editing. **Annarita Baldan:** Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: All co-authors reports financial support was provided by EURAMET European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper

Data Availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

Acknowledgments

The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed by European Union Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and from the Participating States.

Funder name: European Partnership on Metrology

Funder ID: 10.13039/100019599

Grant number: 22NRM03 MetHyTrucks

References

- "2050 long-term strategy," [Online]. Available: (https://ec.europa.eu/clima/eu-action/climate-strategies-targets/2050-long-term-strategy_sv).
- 16ENG01 - Metrology for Hydrogen Vehicles (MetroHyVe1), EURAMET, 2017-2020.
- A European Green Deal," European Commission, [Online]. Available: (https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en).
- Aarhaug, T.A., Bacquart, T., Boyd, R., Daniels, C., 2023a. Review of sampling and analysis of particulate matter in hydrogen fuel. *Int. J. Hydrog. Energy*.
- T.A. Aarhaug, M. Dietrich, A. Kvasnicka, A. Morris, O. Kjos, E. Basset, P. Modugno, S. Khaki, S. Bates, Z. Bikbajeva, C. Blondeel, M. Carré, Y. Lescomez, S. Ferat, Y. Fesselier, N. Chramosta and T. Bacquart, Deliverable D6 - Good Practice Guide for Hydrogen Quality Sampling Procedures/methods At HRS Nozzles (harmonised with USA and Japan), 19ENG04 MetroHyVe2, 2023b.

- ACEA - European Automobile Manufacturers' Association, [Online]. Available: (<https://www.acea.auto/figure/interactive-map-truck-hydrogen-refuelling-stations-needed-in-europe-by-2025-and-2030-per-country/>). [Accessed 12 07 2023].
- Arrhenius, K., Aarhaug, T.A., Bacquart, T., Morris, A., Bartlett, S., Wagner, L., Blondeel, C., Gozlan, B., Lescornez, Y., Chramosta, N., Spitta, C., Basset, E., Nouvelot, Q., Rizand, M., 2021. Strategies for the sampling of hydrogen a refuelling stations for purity assessment. *Int. J. Hydrog. Energy* vol. 46, 34839–34853.
- DOE - The Role of Hydrogen in Transportation," Hydrogen Central, [Online]. Available: <https://hydrogen-central.com/doe-role-hydrogen-transportation>.
- ASTM D7606-7 -Standard Practice for Sampling of High Pressure Hydrogen and Related Fuel Cell Feed Gases, West Conshohocken, Pennsylvania, USA: ASTM International, 2017.
- CCQM-K164 Hydrogen purity, Sevres, FRANCE: Bureau International des Poids et Mesures, 2021.
- Clean Energy Partnership, [Online]. Available: (<https://cleanenergypartnership.de/en/r/efuelling-buses-and-trucks>). [Accessed 17 10 2023].
- Department for Structural and Cohesion Policies, Brussels, Belgium, 2021.
- Directive 2014/68/EU - pressure equipment," [Online]. Available: (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2014/68/oj>). [Accessed 27 02 2024].
- B.D. Ehrhart, G. Bran Anleu, E. Sena, A.B. Muna, D. Ye, E.S. Hecht and C. Rivkin, "Hydrogen Refueling Reference Station Lot Size Analysis for Urban Sites," Sandia National Laboratories report SAN D2020-2796, Albuquerque, New Mexico, 2020.
- EN 17124: Hydrogen fuel - Product specification and quality assurance - Proton exchange membrane (PEM) fuel cell applications for road vehicles, Brussels, Belgium: European Committee for Standardization, 2022.
- Estimation of measurement uncertainty arising from samplingEurachem/EUROLAB/CITAC/Nordtest Guide, 2006.
- European Directive 2010/36/EU," [Online]. Available: (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriiServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2010:162:0001:0135:EN:PDF>). [Accessed 27 02 2024].
- European Green Deal: ambitious new law agreed to deploy sufficient alternative fuels infrastructure, (<https://ec.europa.eu/commission>), 2023.
- High-Flow Prescriptive Fueling Protocols for Gaseous Hydrogen Powered Medium and Heavy-Duty VehiclesSAE J2601-J2605, 2022.
- Horizon Europe, [Online]. Available: (<https://www.horizon-europe.gouv.fr/implémenting-newoptimised-refuelling-protocols-and-components-high-flow-hrs-29681>). [Accessed 14 07 2023].
- Hydrogen Roadmap Europe," Fuel cells and Hydrogen joint undertaking, [Online]. Available: (<https://www.fch.europa.eu/sites/default/files/Hydrogen%20Roadmap%20Europe.Report.pdf>).
- Interactive map - Truck hydrogen refuelling stations needed in Europe by 2025 and 2030, per country [Online]. Available: (<https://www.acea.auto/figure/interactive-map-truck-hydrogen-refuelling-stat>),
- ISO, 2020a. 19880-1: Gaseous hydrogen — Fuelling stations — Part 1: General requirements. International Standardization Organization, Geneva, Switzerland.
- ISO 14687: Hydrogen fuel quality — Product specificationGeneva, Switzerland: International Standardization Organization, 2019.
- ISO 19880-8:2019 - Gaseous hydrogen — Fuelling stations — Part 8: Fuel quality control, Geneva, Switzerland: International Standardization Organization, 2019.
- ISO 21087:2019 - Gas analysis — Analytical methods for hydrogen fuel — Proton exchange membrane (PEM) fuel cell applications for road vehicles, Geneva, Switzerland: International Standardization Organization, 2019.
- ISO/TC 197 WG24 - Gaseous hydrogen – Fuelling protocols for hydrogen-fuelled vehicles, Geneva, Switzerland.
- J2601/2_202307 - Fueling Protocol for Gaseous Hydrogen Powered Heavy Duty Vehicles, SAE International, 2023.
- J2719_202003 - Hydrogen Fuel Quality for Fuel Cell Vehicles," SAE International, 2020.
- JEC Tank-To-Wheels report v5: Heavy duty vehicles," JEC Consortium for the Joint Research Centre (JRC), the European Commission's science and knowledge, 2020.
- Leuenberger, M.C., Schibig, M.F., Nyfeler, P., 2015. Gas adsorption and desorption effects on cylinders and their importance for long-term gas records. *Atmos. Meas. Tech.* vol. 8 (12), 5289–5299.
- M.J. Lighthill, Lighthill, M.J. (1952). "On Sound Generated Aerodynamically. I. General Theory", *Proceedings of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, vol. 211 (1107), p. 564–587, 211 (1107) 1952.
- Mathison, S., 2021. Overview of the SAE J2601 MC Formula H2 Fueling Protocol. Workshop Organ. CEP Hydrog. Eur.
- Metrology for Hydrogen Vehicles 2EURAMET, 19ENG04, 2019-2023.
- Morris, A., Bacquart, T., Blondeel, C., Laudenbach, C., Aarhaug, T., Kjos, O., Dietrich, M., 2023. Good Pract. Guide - Sel. Sampl. Vessels Hydrog. Purity Test. 2, 19ENG04 MetroHyVe.
- Overview Hydrogen Refuelling For Heavy Duty Vehicles, Germany: H2 Mobility, 2021.
- Protocol for heavy duty hydrogen refuelling (PRHYDE), Brussels, Belgium: European Commission, Grant agreement ID: 874997, 2020-2022.
- Refuelling Heavy Duty with very High flow Hydrogen," [Online]. Available: (<https://rheadhy.eu/>). [Accessed 27 02 2024].
- SAE J2799:201912 - Hydrogen Surface Vehicle to Station Communications Hardware and Software," SAE International, 2019.
- Standard J2601_201612 - Fueling Protocols for Light Duty Gaseous HydrogenSAE), 2016.
- Technical report - Minimum Ambient Precooling (MAP) Hydrogen Refueling Protocol for 35MPa Heavy," Clean Energy partnership (CEP), 04 10 2021. [Online]. Available: (https://cleanenergypartnership.de/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/2021-10-04_MG_R_MAP-Fueling-Protocol-for-35-MPa-Heavy-Duty-Vehicles-20-42.5kg_Wenger-Engineering_Rev1.3-min.pdf). [Accessed 22 november 2023].

Further reading

- K. Arrhenius, O. Bükler, S. Bartlett, T. Aarhaug and D. Cortés, 4.1.7 Good practice guide on effective sampling and transportation of hydrogen from the refuelling station as required by ISO14687, 16ENG01 Metrology for hydrogen vehicles, MetroHyVe, 2018.
- ISO 19230:2020 Gas Analysis — Sampling Guidelines, Geneva, Switzerland: International Standardization Organization, 2020b.